

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of furfural by peroxomonosulfuric acid

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Manuscript received 24 December 2004, revised 9 November 2005, accepted 19 January 2006

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of furfural by peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) have been studied in aqueous medium in the pH range 0–4.73 at 308 K. The reactions obey second-order kinetics, first-order each with respect to [furfural] and [PMSA]. The observed V-shaped pH-rate profile has been rationalised by considering the interaction of each HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} with protonated as well as neutral form of the substrate molecule, and suitable rate law has been proposed. Activation energy and thermodynamic parameters of the reactions have been computed.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, furfural, peroxomonosulphuric acid.

Studies relating to the oxidation of furfural and substituted furfurals by metallic and non-metallic oxidants have received a great deal of attention over the years¹. The oxidation involves attack either at the furan ring, or at carbonyl-carbon or both depending on the experimental conditions to yield different products.

In continuation of our work on the oxidation of carbonyl compounds by peroxomonosulfuric acid², we present in this communication a detailed kinetic study of oxidation of furfural by PMSA at different pH in the range 0–4.73 in aqueous medium.

Results and discussion

The rates of oxidation of furfural have been measured at various initial concentrations of PMSA. Under pseudo-first-order conditions, plots of $\log [\text{PMSA}]$ versus time are linear for well over two half-lives indicating the first-order dependence of rate on [PMSA].

Variations in the initial [PMSA] in the range $(3.56\text{--}11.56) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ showed little change in the pseudo-first-order rate constant (Table 1), further showing the first-order dependence of rate on [oxidant].

Table 1 shows the effect of changing initial concentration of substrate on the oxidation rate. The plot of $\log k_1'$ against $\log [\text{substrate}]$ is a straight line ($\gamma = 0.99$) with unit slope, indicating that the order with respect to [substrate] is unity. The second-order rate constants, k_2' , remain constant for varying initial substrate concentrations (Table 1), further showing that the reaction is first-order in the substrate.

Table 1. Second order rate constants for the oxidation of furfural by peroxomonosulfuric acid

Temp. = 308 K, aqueous medium, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$			
$10^2[\text{S}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4[\text{PMSA}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_1'$ s^{-1}	$10^3 k_2'$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
3.40	5.40	0.52	1.53
6.40	5.40	0.99	1.55
12.5	5.41	2.0	1.60
25.7	5.34	3.99	1.55
25.4	3.56	3.72	1.46
25.4	7.83	3.73	1.47
25.4	11.56	3.78	1.49
25.4	5.48	4.01	1.58 ^a
25.6	5.24	3.33	1.30 ^b
25.7	5.10	3.14	1.22 ^c
12.8	5.44	2.57	2.01 ^d
12.8	5.01	3.39	2.64 ^e
12.8	5.01	5.31	4.14 ^f

^a[Acrylamide] = $24.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^b $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^c $\mu = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^d313, ^e318, ^f328 K.

The rate constant for the oxidation of furfural remains unchanged with $[\text{NaClO}_4]$, indicating ionic strength (μ) has no influence on the oxidation rate. Formation of free radicals is also absent as no acrylamide polymerisation is observed during the reaction.

The oxidation process for furfural over the temperature range 308–328 K was studied and the rate constants are recorded in Table 1. The plot of $\log k_2'$ vs T^{-1} has

been found to be linear ($\gamma = 0.99$). The entropy and enthalpy of activation were evaluated by Eyring equation are found to be 36.9 kJ mol^{-1} and $-178.9 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively³.

The kinetics of oxidation of furfural by PMSA have been studied at different pH in the pH range 0–4.73. The rate data are summarised in Table 2. The pH-rate profile is found to be V-shaped with the rate minimum at pH ≈ 1.45 .

Table 2. Oxidation of furfural by peroxomonosulfuric acid at different pH

Temp. = 308 K, aqueous medium		
pH	$10^3 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$10^3 k_2(\text{calcd})$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.0	6.92	6.9
0.3	3.98	3.98
0.69	2.15	2.22
1.0	1.56	1.64
1.45	0.97	1.0
2.0	1.26	1.12
2.5	4.0	3.9
3.1	10.0	14.0
3.77	52.5	60.0
4.73	212.8	279

Rate law and mechanism :

The homolytic cleavage of the peroxide bond requires about 138 kJ mol^{-1} . But the low value of ΔH^\ddagger obtained, in the present study, is significant and offer evidence in favour of polar transition state⁴.

In the pH range 0–1.5 the reaction is found to be acid catalysed and this can be explained by considering the protonation of the carbonyl group and thereby invoking the participation of both neutral as well as protonated forms of the furfural molecule in the reaction.

Both protonated and unprotonated species of benzil, 1,4-cyclohexanedione and aliphatic aldehydes take part in acid catalyzed reactions⁵.

In the pH range studied PMSA exists as HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} (eq. (2))⁶

The oxidation of furfural by PMSA can, therefore, be explained by a mechanism in which the protonated (SH^+) and neutral (S) forms of the aldehyde molecule react simultaneously with HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} in parallel reactions.

The rate law pertaining to these reaction steps are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = k_1 [\text{HSO}_5^-][\text{S}] + k_2 \\ &[\text{HSO}_5^-][\text{SH}^+] + k_3 [\text{SO}_5^{2-}][\text{S}] + k_4 [\text{SO}_5^{2-}][\text{SH}^+] \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

where, $[\text{PMSA}]_t$ represents the total analytical concentration of PMSA and is expressed as

$$[\text{PMSA}]_t = [\text{HSO}_5^-] + [\text{SO}_5^{2-}] \quad (9)$$

The total analytical concentration of aldehyde is given in eq. (10).

$$[\text{S}]_t = [\text{S}] + [\text{SH}^+] \quad (10)$$

From eqs. (2) and (9), we have

$$[\text{HSO}_5^-] = \frac{[\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{H}^+]}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (11)$$

and

$$[\text{SO}_5^{2-}] = \frac{K_1 [\text{PMSA}]_t}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (12)$$

From eqs. (3) and (10), we have

$$[\text{S}] = [\text{S}]_t \left\{ \frac{1}{1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$[\text{SH}^+] = [\text{S}]_t \left\{ \frac{K_2 [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Substituting eqs. (11), (12), (13) and (14) in eq. (8), we get

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = \frac{\left\{ \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + k_3K_1 + k_4K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K_2[\text{H}^+])} \right\} [\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{S}]_t}{(15)}$$

or

$$k'_2 = \frac{\left\{ \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + k_3K_1 + k_4K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K_2[\text{H}^+])} \right\}}{(16)}$$

The average values of k_1 , k_2 , k_3 and k_4 , obtained by least-squares analysis of the data according to eq. (16) are respectively found to be 6.92×10^{-6} , 6.41×10^4 , 4.53×10^6 and $4.92 \times 10^{11} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. These values are in confirmity with the calculated values (Table 2).

Reaction with carbonyl compounds peroxides act as nucleophile⁷ since the peroxy group can attach itself to a reactive site such as an unfilled *p*-orbital of carbonyl-carbon. The Bayer-Villiger reaction represents an extensively investigated example of nucleophilic reactivity of peroxy acids⁸. Acid catalysis is an important feature of these reactions.

In the present study the higher reactivity of SO_5^{2-} as compared to HSO_5^- in reactions with either S or SH^+ , clearly demonstrates the nucleophilic behaviour of PMSA in the reaction. The higher reactivity of protonated ketone as compared to the neutral one, with any particular PMSA species, also parallels the increased electrophilic character of the carbonyl-carbon in the protonated ketone⁵.

The enhancement of rate on either side of the rate minimum observed might be due to an increase in the concentration of more electrophilic substrate species, SH^+ , or due to increase in the concentration of more nucleophilic peroxospecies.

On the basis of foregoing discussions, the stoichiometry and other experimental observations, rate law, and the magnitude of reactivity of different PMSA species, the oxidation of furfural in the pH range 0–4.73, can be visualised to involve a rate-determining nucleophilic attack of peroxy species at the carbonyl-carbon atom of both the neutral as well as the protonated form of furfural molecule resulting in transition states (1) and (2) (corre-

sponding to steps (4) and (6) respectively), followed by rapid oxygen-oxygen bond fission to form the products.

1

2

Experimental

The potassium salt of Caro's acid, Oxone ($2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$) was obtained from Dupont, USA, and was used to prepare PMSA solutions. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Sodium perchlorate, prepared *in situ* by neutralising perchloric acid with carbonate free sodium hydroxide was used for adjusting ionic strength of the medium. All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Acidity of the solution was maintained by adding calculated amounts of HClO_4 or standard buffers. Measurements of pH were made on Digisum Electronics Digital pH meter model DI-707.

For experiments employing $[\text{H}^+] \geq 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the $[\text{H}^+]$ was tritrimetrically determined, and the pH values reported in the range 0–2 refers to the converted values from the measured $[\text{H}^+]$ concentrations.

The kinetics was followed by measuring rate of disappearance of peroxy acid, the estimation of which was made iodometrically using standard thiosulphate. The observed second-order rate constants ($k'_{2\text{obs}}$) was calculated by dividing pseudo-first-order rate constant with respect to peroxy acid disappearance by [substrate]. The rate constants were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$. The self-decomposition of PMSA was found to be either nil or negligibly small under our experimental conditions. The temperature was constant to within $\pm 0.1^\circ \text{C}$.

Stoichiometry : A stoichiometry experiment was conducted at pH = 4 with $\text{PMSA} = 6.55 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, and furfural = $1.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, in aqueous medium. The mixture was allowed to stand at 35°C for 12 h, and the unreacted [PMSA] was then estimated. The

furfural : PMSA ratio for the reaction was found to be $\approx 1 : 1$.

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